
Assessing the Effectiveness and Challenges of Feeding Schemes in Primary Schools in Limpopo Province, South Africa

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ABSTRACT

The National School Nutrition Programme (NSNP) in South Africa aims to improve the health and nutritional status of learners in primary schools in poor rural areas. However, inadequate service provision undermines the effectiveness of the programme, with attendant negative effects on learner health, well-being and academic performance. The study explored the effectiveness of the programme, collaboration and the need for the involvement of both the public and private sectors so as to establish an integrated feeding scheme. The study revealed the need for policy reform, including stricter accountability measures, such as reviews of contracts with suppliers who provide poor-quality food. The PRISMA approach was adopted to conduct content analysis of literature sourced from major scientific databases, namely Google Scholar, Taylor and Francis, Scopus and Web of Science. Findings reveal non-compliance with procurement processes to be the main contributors to poor service quality. Recommendations include more rigorous food safety training for staff, regular inspections by environmental health practitioners, improved procurement standards, and ongoing monitoring and evaluation, supported by multi-sectoral collaborations involving entities such as the Department of Basic Education, municipalities, the Department of Health to enhance programme quality and outcomes.

KEYWORDS: collaboration, evaluation, food safety, monitoring, school feeding scheme, South African schools.

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1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Poverty is a global phenomenon that is particularly prevalent in African countries for various reasons, including a lack of resources, corrupt governance, and failure to adhere to specific rules and regulations (Fagbadebo, 2019). Many primary school-aged children in rural Ethiopian communities, for example, do not attend school because there is insufficient food at home. Consequently, specific policies have been implemented both nationally and internationally to introduce school feeding programmes in Ethiopia (Boreja, 2014). Africa remains the poorest region globally, with a slow decline in poverty rates as compared to other regions (Becker & Frankema, 2019), which include South Africa (Anakudo & Ezenekwe, 2024). Women and children are among the populations most affected by poverty and malnutrition (Ngoma & Mayimbo, 2017). In the poorest countries, school feeding programmes have been introduced with the aim of helping learners focus in class, combating hunger, and increasing enrolment and attendance (Derese & Senapathy, 2023). According to Kiilu and Mugambi (2019), school feeding programmes in primary schools are essential in countries such as Kenya because they promote involvement in school activities and enhance study motivation. Only 36% of learners in Malawi and 56% in Uganda remain in school until grade six, and their primary school completion rates are significantly lower than this (World Bank, 2023). Subsequently, it was adopted in other states in Nigeria and other African countries such as Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Kenya, Mali, Tanzania, Ethiopia, Malawi, Zimbabwe, and Mozambique (Fauziyah & Damilola, 2024). In 1994, the Primary School Feeding Programme was launched by the Department of Basic Education as one of the human rights-based lead initiatives of the Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP) in South Africa (Mabuza, 1997; Nhlapo, Lues, Kativu & Groenewald, 2014). The National School Nutrition Programme (NSNP) subsequently came to serve over 9 million learners in more than 20,000 public schools in South Africa, with goals including the reduction of hunger and the improvement of learner attendance and performance (Devereux et al., 2018).

Nhlapo et al. (2014) report that vitamin A deficiency affects over 25% of children in developing countries throughout the world, and that nutritional disarray is very common in the Free State Province in South Africa. The poor quality of feeding schemes in rural primary schools in Limpopo Province may be attributed to a number of factors, such as the influence of the home and the lack of nutrition information supplied by teachers, who fail to question the type of food provided in schools, even when the food suppliers for school feeding programmes offer options that are not nutrient dense (Magoai, 2019). Dei (2014) makes the observation that, “the lack of nutrition is thus likely to create a vacuum in the process of improving the quality of education in South Africa.” Molotja (2019) states that managing hunger presents a challenge in emerging countries, and notes that since 1990, the number of undernourished individuals has increased by 44 million, illustrating the high rate of population growth in these regions. For learners, proper nutrition is crucial as it enhances both health and academic performance. Reports indicate that most primary school learners in rural areas lack knowledge about nutrient-dense foods, and are not able to assess the quality of the meals supplied to them at school through the NSNP (Molotja, Maliwichi & Jideani, 2020).

In Ndamase (2025) study, it is further revealed that the NSNP was introduced across South Africa schools to address childhood poverty and undernutrition in different schools. Malongane and Mbhenyane (2017) found eating well to encourage academic success and progress. The NSNP is designed to feed learners from low-income backgrounds in rural, farm and informal settlement regions in Limpopo in grades R through 7. Muvhango (2016) asserts that because of hunger and poverty at home, learners in the Vhembe district of Limpopo accept food of poor quality, and consume whatever is offered by the school's food programme. However, there are repercussions to this, with Nhlapo et al. (2015) reporting that: “Children lacking certain nutrients in their diet and who suffer from protein-energy malnutrition, persistent hunger, parasitic infections or other food-related diseases are likely to have a reduced potential for learning compared with healthy, well-nourished children.”

Molotja (2019) reports that there are communities in South Africa that live in extreme poverty resulting in hunger and malnutrition, which compromise the growth and development as well as the learning process of school children. The poor quality of the food supplied through feeding schemes to rural primary schools in Limpopo is a complex problem that results from inadequate community involvement and poor programme management. These factors impede learners' school and academic progress and lead to malnutrition (Ellia, 2017).

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Primary school feeding programmes are essential to learners' academic achievement and improve their quality of life; this is particularly true in the case of those from underprivileged families. School feeding programmes significantly improve the lives of learners from disadvantaged households and promote school attendance even when there is insufficient food at home. The introduction of the NSNP in South Africa has led to a reduction in school absenteeism among learners (Mostert, 2021). Although it is expected that learners will receive nutritious meals at the appropriate times, this is, however, not always the case in some parts of Limpopo (Muvhango, 2016). Poor quality food has detrimental effects on learners that can last a lifetime, and may include obesity and other non-communicable diseases. The study conducted by Sahoo, Sahoo, Choudhury, Sofi, Kumar and Bhadoria (2015) reveal that 35 million of the world's children under the age of 5 live in poor countries, and that over 44 million of the world's children in this age group are obese. Dietary intake is one of the factors contributing to obesity. This is cause for extreme concern, especially given the poor quality of food that learners in public schools in underdeveloped countries consume, as school policies and learner demographics influence the type of food made available to learners in schools.

Godswill, Somtochukwu, Ikechukwu and Kate (2020) explain that deficiency diseases are caused by inadequate vitamin and mineral intake in children's diets. Due to the low quality of food at home, learners whose only healthy meal is the one they receive at school may be at risk of health problems if fruit and vegetables are not included; however, according to research conducted by Faber, Laurie, Maduna, Magudulela and Muehlhoff (2013), rural primary schools covered by school food programmes do not receive fruit and vegetables, despite this being a requirement. Some schools struggle to provide fruit and vegetables or to store them due to inadequate space.

As a consequence of a lack of funds and resources, the school feeding programme in the Sekhukhune district of Limpopo has been reported as frequently serving meals of poor quality (Mbhenyane, Magoai, Mabapa & Tambe, 2022). A disturbing incident occurred at Kwenatshwena Primary School in the Vhembe area in 2014 when more than 100 learners were hospitalised after broken glass was found in the meals provided through the school feeding programme (Tshisikhawe, 2017), and Nomakhushe (2018) states, “South Africa is witnessing increased incidences of hospitalisation of school children, owing to contaminated food provided by state feeding schemes. A factor contributing to the poor quality of food served to learners in Limpopo is untrained food handlers, some of whom are hired not because they are qualified for the job, but because of their relationships with principals, teachers or school governing bodies (Teffo, 2017). Thus, even if a meal contains vitamins and protein, improper handling can still reduce its quality and affect the food served to learners. This is corroborated by a study conducted in South Africa, which found that a lack of adequate facilities can hinder compliance with food safety practices (Chelule & Ranwedzi, 2022).

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The poor quality of food served to learners in public schools is a result of, among other things, inadequate supervision in several districts within Limpopo. Poorly managed schools often struggle with performance and resource allocation, further impacting food quality (Rasila, Kekana & Montja, 2019). Mestry and Du Plessis (2024) attribute inconsistent food provision to inefficient management in schools. In the Mopani district, learners on occasion either do not receive their meal, or the food is supplied after midday and there is no monitoring (Leshabana, 2023). Thus, the lack of management and district assistance have a decided impact on the quality of food served to learners in public primary schools in the province, with suppliers feeling themselves at liberty to supply food of inferior quality because they are aware of the inadequate management. In short, in Limpopo the lack of effective oversight and enforcement mechanisms allows corrupt practices to flourish, leading to compromised food quality and safety in schools (Rangongo, Mohlakwana & Beckmann, 2016).

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What are the contributing factors to the poor quality of feeding schemes in rural primary schools in Limpopo Province, South Africa
- What challenges impact the implementation of feeding schemes?
- What is the current state of school feeding schemes in rural primary schools in Limpopo?

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

4.1 Social Justice Theory

Poor food quality in rural primary schools in Limpopo leads to inequality and the exclusion of learners from low-income families. Social justice theory was considered to be a valuable lens through which to view unfair treatment in the school setting (Khumalo, 2021). For instance, all learners should receive appropriate care, a healthy diet and high-quality food regardless of family background. A scheme that provides free meals is not justified in supplying food of inferior quality, and supplying poor-quality food does not align with the mandate of school feeding programmes. According to Colton and Holmes (2018), a focus on social justice and the preservation of human dignity involves interaction with members of the local community.

4.2 Human Rights-Based Approach (HRBA)

A human rights-based approach was considered relevant to the study. Tibbitts (2024) makes the observation that while learners deserve the right to education because education is crucial to human development, their rights must also be upheld such that they are able to pursue their learning. This could include the right to quality food as provided by school feeding programmes. According to the human rights-based approach, those who possess rights should be accountable and involved in the lives of others so as to prevent their rights from being infringed upon by those who would seek to exploit their circumstances (Broberg & Sano, 2017). Therefore, food suppliers, school principals and district and circuit managers in charge of overseeing the school feeding scheme in Limpopo should be held accountable in instance where food of poor quality is served to learners, as this contravenes their right to receive food of good quality that will support both academic achievement and child development. Hunt (2016) notes that a human rights-based approach to health eliminates inhumane and degrading treatment of people by taking into account both everyone's rights and a high-quality healthcare system for everyone.

5. METHODOLOGY

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Literature Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) approach was applied to enable the researcher to present transparent, comprehensive information demonstrating unbiased reporting. Meta-analyses and systematic reviews help future researchers fill in the gaps in policies (Sewell, Schellinger & Bloss, 2023). PRISMA makes it possible to trace the search for publications and provides transparency (Verastegui, Sandoval-Almazan & Medina-Quintero, 2023). Future researchers could therefore link to, consult and refer to the research that the researcher consulted in order to help close the gap or improve the suggestions made in the study reported on here. Further research on the poor quality of food programmes in rural primary schools in Limpopo may yield recommendations or a way to enhance the services. Karunarathna, Gunasena, De Alvis and Jayawardana (2024) explain that PRISMA involves a structured process for identifying, selecting and analysing relevant studies; in the context of my study, these were studies relevant for a review of the poor quality of feeding programmes in Limpopo.

5.1 Search Strategy and Data Sources

An extensive search was conducted across four recognised and reputable databases: ResearchGate, Taylor & Francis, Google Scholar, and Scopus. These databases were chosen because of their thorough coverage of peer-reviewed academic publications related to feeding schemes in schools and food quality. A scientifically designed search strategy was applied, incorporating key search terms that reflected the scope and focus of the study. These terms included "feeding schemes in primary schools," "rural primary schools," "the quality of food in rural schools," "South African feeding schemes," and "schools in rural South Africa."

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Combining these keywords ensured that the search captured a wide range of relevant studies from various geographical and disciplinary contexts.

5.2 Scholarly Document Selection Phase

The initial search yielded 187 records across the selected databases. Following the removal of duplicate and ineligible records, 101 articles remained for further screening. Following an in-depth review, 81 studies were shortlisted, of which 16 were excluded due to their unrelated focus, which included feeding schemes in African countries other than South Africa. A subsequent screening phase led to the exclusion of 17 additional articles that did not meet the eligibility criteria. Ultimately, 24 peer-reviewed journal articles met all the inclusion criteria and were included in the final analysis for the systematic review.

Figure 1: PRISMA CHART

Inclusion criteria:

- Scholarly documents written in English
- Scholarly articles available online and published between 2013 and 2025
- Global and South African studies relating to the research questions guiding the study
- Global studies on the topic of the poor quality of feeding schemes in rural primary schools in Limpopo province, South Africa

Exclusion criteria:

- Studies not published in English
- Studies published before 2013
- Studies not relating to the quality, implementation and challenges of school feeding schemes
- Journal articles focusing on secondary schools or educational levels other than primary schools.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW

6.1 The factors contributing to the poor quality of feeding schemes in rural primary schools in South Africa

Phetla and Skaal, (2024) explain that since children attending primary school are at a sensitive stage of their physical and mental development, the right nutrients are essential to their growth and development. These authors point out that a rise in food substitution in primary schools has resulted in a high rate of obesity among learners, and identify problems relating to the organisation of feeding programmes (Sanni et al., 2024). Wang, Zhao, Boswell and Rozelle (2018) criticise school feeding programmes in developing countries for being inadequately run, not providing much in the way of nutritious food, and having little effect on learners' health. According to Nhlapo (2024) some of the food provide to rural learners in primary schools lack fruits and vegetables, leading to poor intake of essential micronutrients like vitamin A. Furthermore, the overall dietary diversity is low, with limited food groups being consumed in primary schools in South Africa (Steyn et al., 2015). This makes it worse for rural provinces of South Africa, where schools focus on serving meals cheaply rather than emphasising food quality. Some schools continue to serve competitive food rather than emphasising food quality (Da Silva, Pantoja & Delgrossi, 2023). Furthermore, the NSNP promotes the employment of local women in rural areas; unfortunately, most of these women lack the necessary skills to handle food, which further contributes to the poor quality of food served to learners in primary schools (Gresse, Nomvete & Walter, 2017).

6.2 Problems affecting the implementation of NSNP in Limpopo primary schools

The NSNP resulted in a higher school attendance rate and had a significant impact on the lives of learners in rural communities. However, despite the benefits of the programme, problems were encountered, some of which persist, and which have included inadequate infrastructure, corruption, politicisation, and strained relationships between educators and service providers (Munje & Jita, 2019). This has also affected the daily operations of the programme, compromising not only the quality of food served to learners but also the overall teaching and learning process. Tshisikhawe, Runhare and Litshani (2024) identify the persistent inequality in food supply between urban and rural areas as a serious problem. While urban areas benefit from good infrastructure, such as well-maintained roads, rural areas struggle with food delivery during rainy weather, as poor roads hinder access to some schools. An additional challenge in implementing the primary school feeding programme is that, although regional meetings are essential for overseeing the programme and the expected menu for learners, a poor filing system means that they are not held in the rural districts of Limpopo (Eberlein, 2013)). This affects the entire feeding scheme programme process, since the required district, regional and provincial feedback is not being received, allowing food suppliers and schools that violate the NSNP mandate to avoid repercussions (Lebese, Ngobeni, Sepeng & Phage, 2024). Consequently, the quality of the meals supplied is compromised.

6.3 The current state of school feeding schemes in rural primary schools in Limpopo

Over nine million schoolchildren in South Africa benefit from the school feeding programme (Munje & Jita, 2019). In Limpopo, even though one might expect all districts to adhere to the same standards, the status of the school feeding programme in fact varies depending on how each district manages the programme. The school feeding programme supports 2,747 primary schools in Limpopo, including those in the Capricorn district, which are located in rural and peri-rural areas. Currently, in Limpopo, the programme feeds learners in grades R through 7 (Malongane & Mbhenyane, 2017). According to a study on the success of the school feeding programme in the province, principals, parents, and learners all praised the programme for its crucial role in reducing hunger and increasing school attendance among learners, particularly those from low-income families De Cock, D'Haese, Vink, Van Rooyen, Staelens, Schönfeldt & D'Haese, 2013). A number of studies conducted in Limpopo indicate that the school feeding programme has been implemented in rural primary schools in each of the five districts.

7. DISCUSSION

The study provided information relating to the inadequacy of feeding schemes in rural primary schools in all five districts in Limpopo province, with the poor quality of the meals being supplied to learners being attributed to factors such as political interference, corruption, lack of food handling knowledge on the part of those preparing the food, and inadequate funding inschools. These issues have persisted for a long time, despite instances of the provision of substandard food being reported by researchers and various media outlets. The inferior quality of food in rural primary schools in Limpopo presents families with a difficult situation; even though they are aware of the poor quality of the food given to their children, the level of poverty in which they live means that there is little they can do about it except in instances where learners fall ill and are hospitalised as a result of having consumed the meals supplied, since not allowing their children to receive feeding scheme meals would leave them hungry. A number of recommendations are proposed in the hope of helping to improve the quality of feeding programmes in both the rural primary schools in the five districts in Limpopo as well as other African countries.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the difficulties facing rural primary schools in Limpopo in relation to the poor quality of food supplied to learners, the following recommendations are offered:

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- Food safety training to be attended by all school staff and volunteers involved in the feeding scheme
- Occasional visits by environmental health practitioners, improved norms and standards governing the procurement of goods and services and quarterly monitoring and evaluation meetings to ensure compliance
- Collaboration between the Department of Basic Education, municipalities, the Department of Health, the Department of Labour and service providers so as to ensure the effectiveness and quality of the feeding scheme
- The amendment of certain policies (check Department of Education policies, primary school feeding schemes policies, etc.)
- Assurance that the NSNP programme is grounded in section 18 of the Constitution as part of the declaration of the provision of basic education as a right for all

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